

Learning Scene Semantics from Vehicle-centric Data for City-scale Digital Twins

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Abstract—The creation of digital twins of cityscapes requires the understanding the semantics of relevant objects encountered in the scene, with classes possibly not well covered in standard datasets. In this paper, we assess the generalization capabilities of models for semantic segmentation of street scenes trained on synthetic data to real images. In order to perform assessment on real data, we create a dataset from images obtained from a vehicle-based capture setup, and propose a highly automated annotation pipeline for generating ground truth. We train three state of the art segmentation models on our own synthetic dataset, and evaluate the methods on real data.

Index Terms—Semantic segmentation, digital twin, semi-automatic annotation

I. INTRODUCTION

Digital twins are a powerful paradigm for analysing, exploring and understand real spaces together with relevant data from these environments. The creation of realistic 3D environments that are the backbone of digital twins for large spaces, such as parts of a city, is still a costly and challenging effort. As these environments also undergo constant changes, keeping the digital twin up-to-date is crucial. However, complete re-scans of the environment are not feasible.

One approach to solve this issue is to leverage sensors that are present in the environment to collect information about changes in the environment. In a city environment, today’s vehicles with their rich set of sensors are a logical choice for this purpose. We are thus interested in leveraging content from on-board cameras of cars, which are designed for assistance functions, for collecting data about the environment.

Understanding changes in the scene requires understanding the semantics of regions in the depicted scene, in other words, to perform semantic segmentation. Depending on the application, the relevant classes and the needed granularity differ. For example, digital twin applications supporting city maintenance or planning need to segment classes along the sidewalk, which are irrelevant for automated driving, and thus not covered by datasets created for that purpose. Segmentation algorithms are trained using supervised learning and require

labelled datasets for algorithm development. For the city-scale digital twin creation, we define specific use case requirements that are later translated into datasets through definition of classes and data formats. State of the art datasets generally follow the established standards; however, standardization of data formats for digital twins is the part of the current research efforts.

Using synthetic datasets for training is an alternative in this case, as they allow creating large sets of content together with their annotations for the specific task (such as semantic segmentation). However, while rendering tools have improved, there is still a domain gap between synthetic and real images, as evidenced by the example shown in Fig. 1. Validation results on synthetic data are thus not directly transferable to the target domain. In order to validate on real data, an annotated validation set on real data is needed.

We address these issues in this paper by training state-of-the-art semantic segmentation methods on synthetic data and validating them on a set of real images. In particular, the contributions of this paper are:

- We created a synthetic dataset and captured a real dataset for city environments.
- We propose a highly automated pipeline for annotating a set of real samples for validation, which is also be made publicly available.
- We train three semantic segmentation models on the synthetic dataset and provide results on the real validation dataset.

The rest of this paper is organized in the following manner. Section II provides a review and segmentation approaches and datasets. Section III describes the creation of the synthetic dataset, the capture of the real dataset and the annotation approach. Section IV presents the experiments and their results, and Section V concludes the paper.

II. RELATED WORK

We review related work on semantic and instance segmentation methods, and relevant dataset for training these methods on cityscape scenes.

Fig. 1. Left side: real world image vs. synthetic image on the right.

A. Segmentation

The most widely used class of segmentation methods are still those focusing on visual information only. Swin transformer [1] is a backbone for vision tasks, adding the concept of shifted windows in the attention block, implemented as a hierarchical architecture. The backbone serves a number of downstream tasks, including semantic and instance segmentation. MaskDino [2] is based on the DETR [3] transformed-based object detector and its improved version DINO [4] and adds a mask detection branch to this architecture. OneFormer [5] is a transformer-based model aiming to unify semantic segmentation, instance segmentation and panoptic segmentation with a shared backbone. Mask2Former [6] addresses a similar aim of addressing different segmentation tasks with one architecture, which in this case introduces a transformer decoder with masked attention. BEiT [7] adopts the successful approach of BERT (Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers) from natural language processing, using 16×16 image patches as visual tokens. The model is pretrained by masking patches and then fine-tuned to specific downstream tasks such as semantic segmentation and instance segmentation. InternImage [8] is a vision foundation model, which – in contrast to most other recent foundation models – is not based on transformers but a CNN architecture, proposing an adaptation of deformable convolutions tailored for foundation models. ConvNeXt [9] follows a similar approach, i.e. adopting concepts from vision transformers that can be implemented with the building blocks of a convolutional architecture, thus achieving less complex models performing comparably with transformers.

The emergence of semantic and instance segmentation models backed by vision-language foundation models provided a significant advance over vision-only approaches, in particular for few- and zero-shot tasks. SAM [10] is an early and probably one of the most well-know examples. Pretrained on a large semi-automatically annotated dataset, the model supports prompt-based segmentation using points, boxes or masks. The

TABLE I
URBAN DOMAIN RELATED DATASETS

Dataset	# Images	# Classes	Type
Real Data			
ADE20K	27K	150	RGB
Cityscapes	5K	30	RGB
BDD100K	10K	40	RGB
Waymo dataset	61k	4	Lidar+RGB(D)
Mapillary Vistas	25K	124	RGB
nuImages/nuScenes	93K	25	RGB
Indian Driving	10K	34	RGB
Synthetic Data			
Virtual KITTI	21K	9	RGB(D)
GTA5	25K	19	RGB
SynScapes	25K	19	RGB(D)
SYNTHIA	9K	13	360+RGB(D)
UrbanSyn	7K	19	RGB(D)

model can produce almost complete panoptic segmentations by triggering it on a grid of point prompts. SEEM [11] is another approach from this family, focusing mostly on improving prompting by learning a joint visual-textual prompt embedding. EVA [12] is a foundation model focusing on vision tasks, trained on data aggregated from multiple text-image datasets, by learning to predict masked regions in the images. The model is based on a vision transformer architecture and trained for instance segmentation as one of the downstream tasks. GLEE [13] is a general foundation model backed framework for detection, instance segmentation, tracking, grounding, and identification of arbitrary objects in open world scenarios, trained on a large set harvested from multiple datasets. It also supports prompt-based segmentation.

The versatility of foundation model based approaches, in particular the few- and zero shot capabilities are very appealing in practical applications. However, the runtime is considerably longer than for traditional methods, and the semantic definition of a particular class in the language model may not be known. For example, is a traffic sign just the information carrying front side, or does it include the border, back and possibly pole? We thus see both approaches complementary, in that foundation model backed approaches can serve as a very effective method for generating annotation to be checked by a human in the loop, while a more efficient vision-only segmenter can be trained for the particular purpose.

B. Datasets

While there are some general datasets, such as ADE20K [14], that contain relevant images and classes for street scenes, we are mostly interested in datasets that focus on street scenes, in particular, from a vehicle viewpoint. There is a large number of real datasets that vary in diversity and the number of classes covered. The Cityscapes dataset [15] provides 5K images with instance segmentation annotations for 30 classes. BDD100K [16] is a large-scale dataset for 10 autonomous driving tasks, and 10K images are labelled with instance segmentation annotations for 40 classes.

The Waymo dataset [17] consists of data of 1150 scenes, captured with 5 cameras and LiDAR. Segmentations are provided for four classes. The Mapillary Vistas dataset [18] contains 25K images recorded in different locations, with segmentations for 124 semantic classes (of which 100 are annotated on instance level). nuImages¹, a 2D image dataset provided in connection with nuScenes [19] provides 93K images of 1,000 scenes from 2 cities with segmentations for 25 classes. Indian Driving Dataset (IDD) [20] provides semantic segmentation annotations for 34 classes. All these datasets are available for non-commercial use.

The scarcity of diverse real datasets has sparked interest in generating photo-realistic synthetic data together with annotations for a particular task. Virtual KITTI [21] provides 21K synthetic images with annotations including instance segmentation, covering the nine classes of the KITTI dataset [22]. The GTA5 dataset [23] has been created using the Grand Theft Auto computer game, providing 25K images with semantic segmentation annotations for the 19 classes in the Cityscapes dataset. SynScapes [24] is another dataset providing annotations for the 19 Cityscapes classes on 25K images. SYNTHIA [25] is another synthetic dataset of urban scenes with around 9K images and segmentation labels for 13 classes. UrbanSyn [26] is a very recently proposed synthetic dataset, also providing segmentation results for the 19 Cityscapes classes. It is noteworthy that the authors propose using the dataset for training unsupervised domain adaptation together with the GTA5 and Synscapes datasets.

While there seems to be an abundance of datasets (see Tab. I), most stick to a relatively small set of classes relevant for key automated driving scenarios. However, for digital twin creation, we are also interested in classes related to maintenance of city infrastructure visible from the street, such as trash cans or bus shelters, or checking the presence and readability of road painting (e.g., for speed limit zones). We thus need a synthetic data generation and training pipeline that can be adapted to the required scenarios.

III. DATASET CREATION

Specifically for this work, synthetic and real datasets captured from fisheye cameras have been undistorted to ease the training of segmentation models. This post-processing is done using automated pipelines which are typically configured to work regardless of the data type.

A. Synthetic data generation

Synthetic datasets have been generated using the rFpro² simulation platform as it offers many possibilities including camera sensor modeling, configuration of weather and lighting conditions or definition of static and dynamic objects. The output of the synthetic datasets include both the video stream and the ground truth data including pixel-level segmented frames and additional per-frame metadata. Dataset generation

¹<https://www.nuscenes.org/nuimages>

²<https://rfpro.com>

Fig. 2. Real world sample data of zebra crossings showing the rich variability in color and texture.

has been automated through Python scripts to ease the generation of massive data containing variability over all these different conditions.

Key modeling requirements for the generation of synthetic datasets include the characterization of the virtual cameras in terms of field of view, resolution, distortion model, frame rate and extrinsic parameters among other. This task aims to mimic the same performance of real datasets intended for the final application, with the advantage of adding corner cases which are difficult to source or may add a safety risk if they are created under real conditions. Additionally, environment adaptation to fulfill with DIDYMOS-XR project scope has been considered, including changes on urban furniture, asphalt or road works.

To align with industry standards, the segmented data format has been defined based on Mapillary Vistas dataset [18] as it includes a wide variety of classes aligned with the purpose of this use case. This strategy eases the usage of the tools developed within this project to future work.

B. Real data capture

As it is not possible to develop algorithms purely based on synthetic datasets due to current gaps between virtual and real system performance, which are mainly originated in costly generator fine-tuning and typically manifests in

- too 'clean' synthetic objects that do not reflect the variability of object incarnations (e.g. see Fig. 2),
- deviating levels of detail (LoD) that may bias generalisation capabilities,
- repetitive objects which provoke overfitting.

To overcome these issues, real datasets need to be captured to train and validate the algorithm on the final product. For

Fig. 3. Examples of classes including (a) light post, (b) traffic sign, (c) zebra crossing (c) and (d) cars.

this purpose, real data has been captured using the FICOSA development vehicle which includes a commercial surround-view system based on four 1.3 Mpx fisheye cameras and additional setups intended for data recording and processing.

After each recording campaign, adjusted to specific algorithm needs and use cases, the data is transferred to internal servers for further processing using automated pipelines. This processing includes the validation of data consistency to assure that the recordings are valid and the generation of the outputs required for the algorithm training. It shall be noted that data annotation is not provided by default and manual labelling effort is typically required for the usage of real datasets, limiting the scalability and availability of real data for each specific algorithm requirements.

A set of 500 images with resolution 1344×968 px has been sampled as validation data from the target domain. This subset of the data is made publicly available³ after anonymisation by blurring the pedestrians faces as well as of license plates. Fig. 3 shows examples from the dataset.

C. Semi-automatic data annotation

In order to 'ease the pain' of annotating a large amount of images manually, we have chosen a semi-automatic approach. As explained above, open-vocabulary models backed by vision-language models are a great candidate for annotating real data automatically. However, open-Vocabulary models often face challenges in handling unique classes, and retraining these large models to accommodate them can be computationally intensive. The Hybrid-Panoptic segmenter [27] capitalizes on the broad range of classes offered by Open-Vocab models and supplements them by integrating unique classes through a heuristic process, utilizing closed instance models. The system comprises two primary branches: the open vocab branch and the closed instance segmentation branch. The open vocab branch incorporates ODISE [28], a panoptic method that integrates vision with language models to segment a vast number of classes. The second branch can be any instance segmentation model; in this case, we are using Mask R-CNN, trained specifically on the unique classes that ODISE struggles with. Additionally, the training dataset includes negative frames, which significantly reduces false positives, besides the images containing such classes. Finally, the heuristic block prioritizes the masks predicted by the closed instance branch; specifically, whenever there is a high overlap, the corresponding ODISE mask is replaced by

³<https://zenodo.org/records/12792635>

Fig. 4. Segmentation (a) with hybrid-panoptic, (b) via prompt model.

background pixels, and then the closed mask overrides the intersection values.

For our pipeline, we leverage the following workflow:

- First, an initial panoptic segmentation step with the Hybrid-Panoptic segmenter provides an overview of the existing foreground objects as well as a compilation of background areas that may need to be merged (see Fig. 4 a).
- We then map all labels that require fusion in the repeated panoptic segmentation step.
- If necessary, confidence values are adjusted (lowered to 20%) to get smooth segmentation boundaries.
- In the next step we use the open world segmenter GLEE for selecting the missing segmentation classes with prompts like *all thin lines on the road* e.g. for lane markings and zebra crossings (see Fig. 4 b).
- Manual fine-tuning / correction of invalid class assignments using image-editing tools. This step is mainly necessary for eroded street marks that can not be detected by automatic segmentation.
- Finally, conversion of the color-based masks to class-id masks.

All merge steps are efficiently executed in a Python application, using numpy masks together with the gradio [29] framework.

IV. TRAINING AND EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

For training and evaluation, we use the MMSegmentation Toolbox v1.2.2 [30] running on a server (48 CPU cores, 256GB RAM) with two A6000 GPUs, (10K CUDA cores, 48GB VRAM). We select three different models, BEiT [31], Mask2Former [6] and ConvNeXt [9], all pre-trained on ADE20K checkpoints. with standard configuration settings.

We are training these models with 4006 annotated synthetic FICOSA (rFpro) images, containing a 20% random split per class sampled for validation. For the experiments, 12 out of the 32 classes available on the synthetic dataset are selected, as for those classes at least 50 instances are available in the

Fig. 5. Segmenting new classes on small training data with Mask2Former model on challenging real world conditions.

data.

The list of classes comprises single entities like *Car*, *Wall*, *Road*, *Vegetation*, *Fence*, *Manhole*, *Building*, *Sky* along with the combined class-groups of *Light post/Post/Bollard*, *Traffic Sign Frame/Traffic Sign/Road Sign*, *Parking occupied/Lane marking* and *Road paint stop/Zebra Crossing*.

As visible in Fig. 1, part of the car can be seen in the lower part of the real image. Since it is reflective, it sometimes mirrors objects, and hence leads to false detections. The results on the real data are thus constrained by a region of interest that excludes this lower part of the image (i.e. all pixel below row 711).

Mask2Former and ConvNeXT training process runs 160K iterations in about a day on our machine, while BEiT runs 320K iterations in more than two days.

In the next step, the baseline is calculated over the seven common classes of both datasets using the 500 annotated real images. The baseline-results for the three ADE20K models are summarized on the left side of Table II.

In comparison, the aggregated results from Table III of the seven common classes using the models trained on synthetic data are shown on the right side of Table II.

The higher results of our trained models are partly due to the fact that the real images contain additional classes such as *Bus* in addition to the class *Car*, which are not directly taken into account for the baseline evaluation, although their presence is limited to 10% at most.

The evaluation results for all used classes of the three models in terms of intersection over union (IoU) and mean accuracy (Acc) are listed in Table III.

In addition, the influence of the anonymization service we modelled is also evaluated. There are no differences in the results between the non-anonymized pedestrian faces or car license plates and the blurred ones.

A. Training beyond existing classes

We investigate the efficiency of training models on synthetic data for segmenting new classes which are not part of the pre-trained model – in our case the ADE20K models – by annotating zebra crossings. These are represented in 149 images of the synthetic dataset, which covers 3.7% in the number of images. The quality of the zebra crossings in terms

of coloring and surface coating is higher in the training set than in the real evaluation data, where the stripes show a high degree of natural erosion. As Table III indicates, the benchmark values to detect zebra crossings are remarkably good, and this opens up the possibility of using the models to recognise signs of wear and tear and to record maintenance work in the road area.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we address the issue of evaluating the generalization capabilities of semantic segmentation models trained on synthetic data from city environments to real data. In order to perform the validation on real data, we propose a highly automated annotation workflow using a hybrid panoptic segmentation model and a language model backed segmenter. We provide evaluation results for three state-of-the-art segmentation models on the real data.

Compared to the baseline drawn from the pre-trained models, we conclude that training on a rather small synthetic dataset increases the model capabilities to segment existing and new classes properly, although it is important that the synthetically generated data reflect the reality well, in order to achieve optimal segmentation results.

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TABLE II
BASELINE (BL) IOU AND ACCURACY, COMPARED TO FICOSA IOU AND ACCURACY

Class	BEiT (BL)		Mask2Former (BL)		ConfNeXt (BL)		BEiT (FICOSA)		Mask2Former (FICOSA)		ConfNeXt (FICOSA)	
	IoU	Acc	IoU	Acc	IoU	Acc	IoU	Acc	IoU	Acc	IoU	Acc
wall	0.23	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	7.00	0.02	0.23	11.40	0.02	0.23
building	59.61	82.02	58.84	80.93	43.01	48.50	91.11	56.13	91.93	93.73	75.47	95.44
sky	92.42	99.02	92.07	97.63	90.81	92.67	97.46	92.26	98.15	98.52	98.68	99.26
tree	56.77	58.74	49.25	51.35	58.34	67.72	82.70	63.80	86.40	92.94	77.82	93.13
road	87.88	96.32	89.51	98.21	87.41	96.53	99.54	84.04	99.67	99.87	92.47	99.80
car	68.65	74.20	69.27	73.44	67.68	75.83	93.61	68.79	93.38	97.27	95.36	96.40
fence	23.65	36.08	10.57	18.34	13.31	38.89	70.72	70.72	69.66	75.29	70.72	72.72
average	55.57	63.77	52.79	59.99	51.51	60.02	77.06	79.57	77.45	81.29	52.15	62.86

TABLE III
IOU AND ACCURACY OF MASK2FORMER, CONVNEXT AND BEiT

Class	Intersection over Union (IoU)			Accuracy (Acc)		
	Mask2Former	ConfNeXt	BEiT	Mask2Former	ConfNeXt	BEiT
Car	93.61	68.79	93.38	97.27	95.36	96.40
Light post/Post/Bollard	12.11	0.80	12.47	13.67	5.35	13.02
Wall	7.00	0.02	0.23	11.40	0.02	0.23
Traffic Sign Frame/Traffic Sign/Road Sign	78.31	6.10	73.69	85.25	41.84	79.84
Parking occupied/Lane marking	91.21	7.41	93.03	93.77	15.50	97.72
Road paint stop/Zebra Crossing	86.95	10.49	87.48	91.94	14.36	92.41
Road	99.54	84.04	99.67	99.87	92.47	99.80
Vegetation	82.70	63.80	86.40	92.94	77.82	93.13
Fence	70.72	0.00	69.66	75.29	0.00	72.72
Manhole	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Building	91.11	56.13	91.93	93.73	75.47	95.44
Sky	97.46	92.26	98.15	98.52	98.68	99.26
average	67.56	32.49	67.17	71.14	43.09	70.00

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